

Education Quarterly Reviews

Prastyanti, S., Adi, T. N., Sulaiman, A. I., & Windiasih, R. (2022). Education Services for Students during the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 5(3), 325-333.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.05.03.548

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Education Services for Students during the Covid-19 Pandemic

Shinta Prastyanti¹, Tri Nugroho Adi², Adhi Iman Sulaiman³, Rili Windiasih⁴

^{1,2,3} Communication Science Department, Jenderal Soedirman University, Indonesia

⁴ Department of Sociology Studies, Jenderal Soedirman University, Indonesia

Correspondence: Adhi Iman Sulaiman, Lecturer & Researcher in Communication Science Department, Faculty of Social and Political Science, Jenderal Soedirman University, Indonesia. Email: adhi.2005unsoed@gmail.com

Abstract

The Corona Virus Disease 19 currently has disrupted all aspects of life, including education. The teachers and students have to adapt to the studying and learning process and how to serve students. This phenomenon is important and interesting to study. The research uses a qualitative case study method with data collection through observation, dialogical interviews, Focus Group Discussion, Participatory Decision Making, and documentation analysis. Informants are teachers represented from the fifth-grade elementary schools, both urban and rural areas, besides the principals, educational leaders, and practitioners in the District of Banyumas, the Province of Middle Java, Indonesia. The research analysis uses interactive analysis starting from data collection, data reduction, verification, and triangulation till the conclusion drawing. The results showed that teachers and students in research areas alike experienced technological disruption both in the educational process or services to students during the pandemic as an effect of the changing of studying learning methods from face-to-face to online. Another result found the use of digital media in the process of implementing and evaluating the studying learning process hurts boredom, lack of concentration on the lesson, and humanistic interaction with other students. In contrast, the result also found a positive impact such as interesting and innovative digital applications that can support the educational process during that pandemic. It is necessary to socialize, adapt, adopt innovation and increase competence for teachers and students, especially in the use of digital-based learning media and applications (online) including quality assurance of the education implementation and evaluation process.

Keywords: Education Services, School Students, Educational Media, Innovation Adoption, Covid-19 Pandemic

1. Introduction

The educational process during the Covid 19 pandemic in Indonesia, which began in early 2020, underwent a significant change, from face-to-face or offline (outside the internet network) between teachers or teachers and teaching participants or students to an online or online learning process (in a network). This is due to the increasing number of Covid-19 sufferers, not only in Indonesia but throughout the world. As data shown by the Indonesian Covid-19 Team (covid19.go.id) from March to July 2020 of 80 thousand cases. It jumped to 4.2 million in December 2021. All public activities and community mobilization are limited. Economic, social, religious activities (worship), tourism, and transportation including education were also affected. To support that effort the

government issued the policy of Large-Scale Social Restrictions with government policies that imposed several government regulations such as Government Regulation Number 21 of 2020 concerning Large-Scale Social Restrictions in the Context of Accelerating Handling of Covid-19 and Regulation of the Minister of Health Number 9 of 2020 concerning Guidelines for Scaled Social Restrictions. Big in the context of accelerating the acceleration of handling Covid 19. The two regulations are a form of elaboration and implementation of Law Number 6 of 2018 concerning Health Quarantine which also has legal consequences for violations.

Based on the researcher's preliminary study from the end of 2020 to the middle of 2021, particularly in the education process, the policy regarding the regulation of Large-Scale Social Restrictions and the Enforcement of Restrictions on Community Activities resulted in several major changes. Adaptation to conditions and situations during the educational process and students' services such as face-to-face to online digital media through google meetings, zoom meetings, or other e-learning media was necessary.

The learning atmosphere in the digital era must be balanced among access skills, quotas, and the quality of the network. The development of online digital media for learning must be increased not only during a pandemic, but it has to become a necessity and a challenge in the digital era as a form of E-Learning (Electronic Learning) process. An electronic learning system with computer and internet technology can support a learning process remotely without having to meet face-to-face between teachers and students (Amichai, 2009; Aviram & Dotan, 2009; Babbar & Gupta, 2022; Clark & Gibb, 2006; Greitzer, 2002; Michael, 2003; Schweizer, 2004; Suswanto et al. 2021).

The learning process with digital online media is a form of mass communication where the communication process uses electronic or print media that is uploaded and can be downloaded by all parties as long as has access and device. That has become a challenge and need for a lifestyle where contemporary culture in the media reflects the culture of the community. Media is a window of reality that expands perception and mirrors distorted events so that meaning changes because it is constructed by other people through that media itself. Then it developed to become a new media that used networks, access, and the internet that disrupted the pattern of life in all fields. It also cannot be separated from the internet world to become an internet society.

The new media era and the era of disruption have emphasized that electronic media expands perceptions (thoughts) in the context of the global village. Internet media is called cyberspace and it is intentionally created as Netizen-Computerization-Internet-Digital. The disruption era and innovator dilemma (interference from technology), gives a fundamental change from the old to a new system in various aspects of life. According to the technological or industrial revolution, the characteristics of the 4.0 industrial revolution emphasize the digital economy, artificial intelligence, big data, and robotics (disruptive innovation). The era of digital learning media with the existence of an electronic learning system (e-learning) and a Learning Management System on the website of educational institutions (Aquilar & Buonanno, 2019; Edwards & Magill, 2022; Jiang, 2022; Menke & Schwarzenegger, 2019; Picone, 2017).

The research on education and services to students during the Covid-19 pandemic towards the new normal era is strategic and important to evaluate material as well as a significant contribution, especially in the learning process as a challenge and need in the digital era. It is expected to contribute to effective and quality learning outcomes.

2. Research Method

This research uses qualitative research with case studies that deeply investigate the phenomena of reality where the interaction with the environment of a social unit such as individuals, institutions, communities, or society as the background (Bitektine, 2008; Hennings et al., 1996). The data on qualitative research methods were collected through observation, dialogue or interviews, brainstorming, Focus Group Discussion, Participatory Decision Making, and documentation analysis.

The informants are selected by purposive sampling technique, which is based on some consideration of the representation of a community and the research subject or informant can provide the information needed for

research. The research location considers the representation of public and private schools in urban and rural areas (two public elementary schools and two private elementary schools in urban and rural areas) in the District of Banyumas Regency, Central Java Province, Indonesia. Research informants were administrators of school foundations, principals, teachers as representatives of fifth-grade of elementary schools, educational leaders, and practitioners.

Research data analysis using interactive analysis: (1) Data reduction, which is the process of selecting, centralizing, simplifying, and classifying raw data that emerges from written notes in the field, which takes place continuously during the research. (2) Data presentation is a structured collection of information that gives the possibility of drawing conclusions and taking action. (3) Drawing conclusions or verification (Miles & Huberman 2019).

The process of research stages is designed to produce: (1) discovery and theory development; (2) Applied research & advanced research. This is an informative model from Havelock modified by Mardikanto and Soebiato (2013).

Figure 1: The Process of Implementing Research Activities

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Educational Challenges in the Covid-19 Era

Based on the results of previous studies found a very important and strategic potential in the process of education and student services in the Covid-19 pandemic era, namely (1) the learning process from face to face between teachers and teaching participants by attending school (Offline) changed to indirectly learning process through online media. (2) The more flexible learning process schedule, is conducted directly online or synchronously (real-time through digital media such as google meetings, zoom meetings, chats, and video calls). While asynchronous or indirect online as a communication pattern that is delayed or can be delayed at a very flexible time through digital online media such as Websites or the World Wide Web, e-mail, forums, and read/write online documents through LMS or Learning Management System as a software application for online activities, electronic learning programs. (3) Learning media has become more diverse, especially through online digital media such as google meetings, zoom meetings, chats, and video calls, as well as the Learning Management System. (4) Learning media and services based on digital innovation media keep being used continuously as a complement to learning processes and media in the new normal era which are very innovative, creative, productive, and effective.

The barriers in distance learning programs such as feeling bored because there is no direct/face-to-face interaction, a lack of understanding of teaching materials, and delayed feedback of the questions and assignments given

without complete guidance about it. The distance education system requires an academic program in the form of face-to-face tutorial services to optimally help students in the process of learning (Chaney, 2009; Diwan & Dumblekar, 2000; Huebner & Wiener, 2001; Teenant et al., 2005). Based on the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture number 24 of 2012 concerning the Implementation of Distance Education in Higher Education, Article 1 (4) states that tutorials are a form of academic learning assistance that can be carried out face-to-face or through the use of information and communication technology device.

The development of the education system in the era of globalization and digitalization cannot be separated from web and internet-based technology media. However, face-to-face learning still has to be carried out with appropriate learning methods to achieve the objectives and expected outcomes besides motoric skills and behavioral attitudes changes. The tutorial method facilitates and motivates students to think, learn, observe, behave and carry out the goals of each course. Besides the student, the ability of the tutor to become a facilitator or teacher will determine the success of the tutorial method (Basak et al., 2018; Blonna & Shapiro, 2001; Chaney et al., 2009; Costarides, 2014; Mathew, 2014; Sulaiman). & Ahmadi, 2020).

Some important finding of the research is (1) Limited ownership of the device and online digital access due to economically disadvantaged and networks barrier, (2) Lack of ability to adopt online digital media innovations for e-learning of particular teachers and students, and (3) Support and assistance to the adaptation of digital technology in the learning process such as training and workshop is still necessary, (4) Undirect interaction between teachers and students in the learning process with the school environment create a saturation. Those problems need serious attention.

The process of socialization and adaptation to the use of digital technology media in the education process and services to students is still needed because the ability to use digital technology media during the pandemic can be useful for the New Normal era.

3.2. The standardization of innovative education in the Covid-19 era

The research linked to implementation and commitment of educational institutions in developing rural resources and local wisdom to the topic of gender, children, and community services, especially in rural education as a form of social engineering and community empowerment.

The digital innovation-based of education and service model for students in the Covid-19 pandemic era towards the New Norm Era is very important for supporting creative, innovative, and productive education in developing the capacity and quality of human resources. The target of this research is very strategic and important for the development of science, both in terms of concept and practical aspects. This research is determined through a series of studies from the research findings.

The preliminary research was conducted from the end of 2021 to mid-2022 on the process of education and services for students based on digital innovation during the pandemic era towards the new normal era. A series of discussions and studies were conducted with the research team, colleagues, practitioners, and experts. Based on the similarities and differences in research and preliminary studies, a formulation of the problem, objectives, methodology, and research locations is determined to the state of the art and research novelty.

Based on Law No. 18 of 2002 concerning the National System for the Development and Application of Science and Technology, Diffusion is an activity of adoption (acceptance and application), and the application of innovation results to increase its potential utilization. While, innovation is research, development, and/or engineering activities to develop the practical application and value of science and technology into products or production processes. According to Rogers (2003), the innovation adoption process consists of (1) Awareness: the existence of an innovation policy action (Knowledge), (2) Interest: gathering interest about information (push), and (3) Evaluation: reflection of advantages and disadvantages (Decision accept /reject), (4) Experiment: Testing innovation change (Implementation and practice), (5) Adoption.

The process of adopting technological innovation is a process of accepting new things, which can be seen in the behavior of individuals or groups, while technological innovation is a process of creativity to produce new products or modify products to provide more usability and meet market demands. Those factors that determine the adoption of technological innovations are the type of entrepreneurship, business scale, availability of credit and labor, entrepreneur characteristics factors (such as age, education, and attitude towards the risk or entrepreneurial ability), situational factors (such as market conditions), psychological factors of the innovation recipient, attitudes and values adopted by the community, and communication networks, as well as the type of innovation itself (Jeannot & Jolibert, 2013; Link & Reece, 2021; Peltier et al., 2012; Prastyanti et al., 2020; Sok et al., 2013; Sulaiman et al., 2022; Voola et al., 2012).

Management has some elements that cannot be separated or complemented from each other. since planning, organizing, implementing to evaluating. The success and effectiveness of management with accurate decisions, proper evaluation activities, and accurate information data are needed to measure. Evaluation is needed to identify problems and opportunities to meet and assess needs and explain the relevant context. Evaluation can be conducted in all stages. The results of the evaluation provide important recommendations for the next decision-making or strategies to maintain, modify or improve what is no longer relevant (Attfield, 1999; Campbell-Patton, 2016; Chouinard & Cousins, 2009; Delgado et al., 2021; Lumino & Gambardella, 2020; Sulaiman et al., 2020; Stufflebeam 2007).

Management and education quality standards during the Covid-19 Pandemic through the media of technological innovation require collaborative support among some relevant stakeholders as shown in Table 1:

Table 1: The Important Role of Partnership

Engaged Partners	Partnership Benefits
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The educational institutions involved as research subjects were 2 favorite public elementary schools in Purwokerto: Sokanegara State Elementary School and Kranji State Elementary School and 2 favorite private elementary schools: Al-Irsyad Elementary School and Al-Azhar Elementary School, as well as 4 elementary schools. 2. Involving a community of educational activists, experts, and practitioners as well as academics for empowering education in the villages who are involved in the process and use of research findings for social engineering that is more useful for improving the competence of elementary schools in rural areas. 3. The village government, the mass media community, and the private sector participate and support the implementation of the benefits of research activities. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Partners are participative and involved in the research process to identify and analyze problems, potentials, and prospects as a more advanced rural education social engineering effort. 2. Partners being resource persons, instructors, facilitators, and assistants in research and implementation of student education and service models in the Covid-19 Pandemic era towards the New Normal Era are very important in supporting creative, innovative, and productive education 3. The location and research results can be used for further research, community service, lecture assignments, practicums, internships, and student real-work lectures

Characteristics in face-to-face education programs can be identified and analyzed with these three important components: planning, implementation, and program outcomes. For developing a face-to-face tutorial program evaluation strategy, those three components can be implemented in the evaluation strategy of planning, implementation, and tutorial results. (1) Evaluation of the planning component is focused on perceptions of program management, independence in learning, and the perceptions of tutorial places and facilities. (2) Evaluation of program implementation is focused on the quality of the tutorial process. (3) Evaluation of program results is focused on satisfaction with the learning outcomes (Farmer & Koehler, 2022; Ferdianto & Rusman, 2018; Hardman, 2005; Jones, 2012; Schröter & Alyami, 2012; Sabiq et al., 2021).

Evaluation is an activity of collecting, analyzing, and presenting important data and information which is being considered for better decisions with relevant indicators such as readiness of the teachers and organizing team, and completeness of infrastructure or facilities. Evaluation of tutorial programs to assess quality assurance in the

implementation of the Distance Learning Program Unit provides open opportunities for students to be involved in evaluating the tutorial process itself on a regular and continuous basis at each tutorial stage using the "Tutor Evaluation Questionnaire" instrument (Azar et al., 2021; Sahling & De Carvalho, 2021; Poole, 2020; Veletsianos et al., 2022).

Quality educational institutions require effective and efficient institutional management from the aspect of human resources, funds, and infrastructure as well as open and adaptive leaders and teachers to achieve goals. Quality standard education is not only judged by the quality of its graduates but also by other indicators: (1) customer satisfaction, (2) increased customer interest and expectations, and (3) customer delight (Lewis 2002; Sallis, 2006).

Based to the National Education Standards Agency that the National Education Standards (2019) consist of (1) Graduate Competency Standards, (2) Content Standards, (3) Process Standards, (4) Education and Education Personnel Standards, (5) Facilities and Infrastructure Standards, (6) Management Standards, (7) Education Financing Standards, (8) Educational Assessment Standards (Source: Minister of Education Regulation number 44 of 2015 concerning National Higher Education Standards Article 1 paragraph 4).

Based on a study of the importance of the educational process and services to students in the Covid-19 pandemic era through the use of innovative new media such as information technology media contribute to carrying out quality management standardization of educational evaluation. Then the model can be designed in Figure 2 as follows.

Figure 2: Education Quality Management in the Covid-19 Period

3. Conclusion

The process of education and services to students in urban and rural schools during the Covid-19 Pandemic, especially in 2020-2021, experienced technological disruption, which was initiated from direct face-to-face then drastically changed to indirectly using internet technology media with lack of the device and network quality.

The education actors both teachers and students in urban and rural schools faced difficulty in adapting to online

media and educational applications because they did not access them before the Covid-19 pandemic.

Schools and teachers including students need socialization, adaptation, and adoption of media innovations and applications of digital technology such as in E-Learning (Electronic Learning) which is an electronic learning system with computer and internet technology that can support a distance digital learning process without having to direct interaction.

Media and educational applications used in the educational process and services to students during the Covid-19 pandemic are Google meetings, Zoom meetings, Microsoft Teams, and Chat and video calls via social media. However, building a Learning Management System in elementary schools has not yet been realized.

The negative impact of using digital media in the process of implementing education during the Covid-19 pandemic is saturation and lack of concentration and humanistic interaction with students because they cannot meet the face. However, the positive impact of using digital educational media is creating a more varied, effective, attractive, and innovative educational process, and possible to continue it in the New Era.

References

- Amichai-Hamburger, Y. (2009). E-Learning: Is Technology the Lighthouse?. *Policy Futures in Education*, 7(6), 601–606. <https://doi.org/10.2304/pfie.2009.7.6.601>
- Aquilar, A.M., & Ballard, D.I. (2022). *Even Heroes Need Help: The Impact of COVID-19 on Physicians Already at Risk for Burnout*. In: Browning, L.D., Sørnes, J.O., Svenkerud, P.J. (eds) *Organizational Communication and Technology in the Time of Coronavirus*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-94814-6_17
- Attfield, D.G. (1999). Three Phases of Religious Education: Learning, Evaluation and Commitment. *Journal of Education and Christian Belief*, 3(2), 123–135. <https://doi.org/10.1177/205699719900300207>
- Aviram, A., & Dotan, I. (2009). When the Virtual Meets Virtue: From E-Learning to E-Education. *Policy Futures in Education*, 7(6), 581–586. <https://doi.org/10.2304/pfie.2009.7.6.581>
- Azar, A. J., Khamis, A. H., Naidoo, N., Lindsbro, M., Boukhaled, J. H., Gonuguntla, S., Davis, D., & Banerjee, Y. (2021). Design, Implementation and Evaluation of a Distance Learning Framework to Expedite Medical Education during COVID-19 pandemic: A Proof-of-Concept Study. *Journal of Medical Education and Curricular Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23821205211000349>
- Babbar, M., & Gupta, T. (2022). Response of educational institutions to COVID-19 pandemic: An inter-country comparison. *Policy Futures in Education*, 20(4), 469–491. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14782103211021937>
- Basak, S.K., Wotto, M., & Bélanger, P. (2018). E-learning, M-learning and D-learning: Conceptual definition and comparative analysis. *E-Learning and Digital Media*, 15(4), 191–216. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2042753018785180>
- Bitektine, A. (2008). Prospective Case Study Design: Qualitative Method for Deductive Theory Testing. *Organizational Research Methods*, 11(1), 160–180. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428106292900>
- Blonna, R., & Shapiro, P. J. (2001). Learning at a Distance. *Health Promotion Practice*, 2(3), 198–202. <https://doi.org/10.1177/152483990100200302>
- Buonanno, M. (2019). Seriality: Development and disruption in the contemporary medial and cultural environment. *Critical Studies in Television*, 14(2), 187–203. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1749602019834667>
- Campbell-Patton, C. (2016). Book Review: Peace Education Evaluation: Learning From Experience and Exploring prospects. *American Journal of Evaluation*, 37(4), 580–583. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098214016637674>
- Chaney, B.H., Eddy, J.M., Dorman, S.M., Glessner, L.L., Green, B. L., & Lara-Alecio, R. (2009). A Primer on Quality Indicators of Distance Education. *Health Promotion Practice*, 10(2), 222–231. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1524839906298498>
- Chouinard, J. A., & Cousins, J. B. (2009). A Review and Synthesis of Current Research on Cross-Cultural Evaluation. *American Journal of Evaluation*, 30(4), 457–494. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098214009349865>
- Christensen. C.M. (1997). *The Innovator Dilemma. When Technologies Coalesce Greatfirm to Fail*. Boston Massachusetts: Harvard Bisnis School Press
- Clark, D.N., & Gibb, J.L. (2006). Virtual Team Learning: An Introductory Study Team Exercise. *Journal of Management Education*, 30(6), 765–787. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1052562906287969>
- Costarides, M.V. (2014). Knowledge Management and E-Learning. *Health Promotion Practice*, 15(6), 790–794. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1524839914548451>

- Delgado, F., Flores, M.E., & Nájera, A.J. (2021). Lessons in the Use of Technology for Science Education during COVID-19 Age under a Teachers' Collaboration Cluster. *Education Sciences*, 11(9), 543. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11090543>
- Derouin, R. E., Fritzsche, B. A., & Salas, E. (2005). E-Learning in Organizations. *Journal of Management*, 31(6), 920–940. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206305279815>
- Diwan, P., & Dumblekar, V. (2000). Internet-Based Distance Education. *Paradigm*, 4(1), 51–62. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0971890720000106>
- Doerfel, M.L., & Haseki, M. (2015). Networks, disrupted: Media use as an organizing mechanism for rebuilding. *New Media & Society*, 17(3), 432–452. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444813505362>
- Edwards, W., & Magill, K.R. (2022). Rethinking the educational ecology in the wake of COVID: Intellectual solidarity, teacher prestige, and educational humanization. *Policy Futures in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14782103221101762>
- Farmer, T., & Koehler, A. (2022). Design Judgments in the Creation of eLearning Modules. *Journal of Formative Design in Learning*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41686-022-00063-3>
- Ferdianto, V.B., & Rusman., (2018). Evaluation the implementation of local content curriculum of local language and environmental education. *Jurnal Penelitian Ilmu Pendidikan*. 11(2): 117-128, [doi:https://doi.org/10.21831/jpipfip.v11i2.19542](https://doi.org/10.21831/jpipfip.v11i2.19542)
- Greitzer, F.L. (2002). A Cognitive Approach to Student-Centered E-Learning. *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, 46(25), 2064–2068. <https://doi.org/10.1177/154193120204602515>
- Hardman, J. (2005). Book Review: Ethnography for Education. *Journal of Research in International Education*, 4(1), 110–113. <https://doi.org/10.1177/147524090500400107>
- Hennings, J., Williams, J., & Haque, B. N. (1996). Exploring the health needs of Bangladeshi women: a case study in using qualitative research methods. *Health Education Journal*, 55(1), 11–23. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001789699605500103>
- Huebner, K.M., & Wiener, W.R. (2001). Distance Education in 2001. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness*, 95(9), 517–524. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0145482X0109500902>
- Jeannot, F., & Jolibert, A. (2013). Temporal distance, mental simulation and the adoption of complex technological innovations. *Recherche et Applications En Marketing (English Edition)*, 28(1), 65–84. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2051570713480725>
- Jiang, X., Mao, T., & Tian, J. (2022). The Application of Digital Technology in the Complex Situation of News Dissemination from the Perspective of New Media Art, *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, Special Issue. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/1685430>
- Jones, G. (2012). Book review: Evaluation in distance education and e-learning: The unfolding model. *Journal of Research in International Education*, 11(1), 106–110. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1475240911431665>
- Lewis, P.V. (2002). Organizational Communication: The Essence of Management, dalam Syafaruddin, *Manajemen Mutu Terpadu dalam Pendidikan* Jakarta: Grasindo
- Link, T.C., & Reece, B. (2021). Barriers to the Adoption of Technological Innovations in Corrections: A Review and Case Study. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 65(2–3), 262–281. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624X20952396>
- Littlejohn, S.W. (2005). *Theories of Human Communication*. Canada: Wadsworth
- Lumino, R., & Gambardella, D. (2020). Re-framing accountability and learning through evaluation: Insights from the Italian higher education evaluation system. *Evaluation*, 26(2), 147–165. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356389019901304>
- Mardikanto, T., & Soebiato, P. (2013). *Pemberdayaan Masyarakat dalam Perspektif Kebijakan Publik*. Bandung : Penerbit Alfabeta.
- Mathew, D. (2014). E-Learning, Time and Unconscious Thinking. *E-Learning and Digital Media*, 11(2), 135–140. <https://doi.org/10.2304/elea.2014.11.2.135>
- McMullan, J. (2020). A new understanding of 'New Media': Online platforms as digital mediums. *Convergence*, 26(2), 287–301. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354856517738159>
- McQuail, D. (2010). *McQuail's Mass Communication Theory*. Los Angeles, London, New Delhi, Singapore & Washington DC: Sage Publication Ltd
- Menke, M., & Schwarzenegger, C. (2019). On the relativity of old and new media: A lifeworld perspective. *Convergence*, 25(4), 657–672. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354856519834480>
- Michael, A.W. (2003). *Michael Allen's Guide to E-learning*. New Jersey USA : John Wiley and Sons Inc
- Miles, M.B., Huberman, A.M., & Saldana, J. (2019). *Qualitative Data Analysis: A Methods Sourcebook*. Arizona State University, USA: SAGE Publications, Inc
- Peltier, J. W., Zhao, Y., & Schibrowsky, J. A. (2012). Technology adoption by small businesses: An exploratory study of the interrelationships of owner and environmental factors. *International Small Business Journal*, 30(4), 406–431. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0266242610365512>
- Picone, I. (2017). Conceptualizing media users across media: The case for 'media user/use' as analytical concepts. *Convergence*, 23(4), 378–390. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354856517700380>

- Poole, A. (2020). Constructing International School Teacher Identity from Lived Experience: A Fresh Conceptual Framework. *Journal of Research in International Education*, 19(2), 155–171. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1475240920954044>
- Prastyanti, S., Subejo., & Sulhan, M. (2020). New Media Access and Use for Triggering the Farmers Capability Improvement in Central Java Indonesia. *Humanities and Social Science Research*, 3(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.30560/hssr.v3n1p1>
- Rogers, E.M. (2003). *Diffusion of Innovations*. New York, London, Toronto : Free Press
- Sabiq, A., Sulaiman, A.I., & Sugito, T. (2021). Designing Family Empowerment Program: Community Education in Times of Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Educational Research*, 3(3), 22-32. <https://doi.org/10.30560/ier.v3n3p22>
- Sahling, J., & De Carvalho, R. (2021). Understanding Teacher Identity as an International Teacher: An Autoethnographic Approach to (Developing) Reflective Practice. *Journal of Research in International Education*, 20(1), 33–49. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14752409211005380>
- Sallis, E. (2006). *Total Quality in Education, Manajemen Mutu Pendidikan*, terj. Ahmad Ali Riyadi & Fahrussozi. Yogyakarta: IRCiSOD
- Schröter, D., & Alyami, M. (2012). Book Review: Evaluation in Distance Education and E-Learning: The Unfolding Model. *American Journal of Evaluation*, 33(1), 143–145. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098214011411576>
- Schweizer, H. (2004). E-Learning in Business. *Journal of Management Education*, 28(6), 674–692. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1052562903252658>
- Sok, P., O’Cass, A., & Sok, K. M. (2013). Achieving Superior SME Performance: Overarching Role of Marketing, Innovation, and Learning Capabilities. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 21(3), 161–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ausmj.2013.04.001>
- Sulaiman, A.I., & Ahmadi, D. (2020). Empowerment Communication in an Islamic Boarding School as a Medium of Harmonization. *Jurnal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 36(4) 2020: 323-338.
- Sulaiman, A.I., Chusmeru., Adi, T.A., Jati, P.I.P., Runtiko, A.G., & Sutikna, N. (2020). Empowerment Program Design in Edutourism Management Post Pandemic Covid 19. *Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 3(3), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.30560/jems.v3n3p1>
- Sulaiman, A.I., Weningsih, S., Sugito, T., Masrukin., & Suswanto, B. (2022). Economic Empowerment Model in Harmonization and Deradicalization of Islamic Boarding School. *Journal of Positive Psychology and Wellbeing*, 6(1), 2318-2335. <https://journalppw.com/index.php/jppw/article/view/2998>
- Suswanto, B., Sulaiman, A.I., Sugito, T., Weningsih, S., Sabiq, A. Kuncoro, B. (2021). Designing Online Learning Evaluation in Times of Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Educational Research*, 4(1), 18-28. <https://doi.org/10.30560/ier.v4n1p18>
- Stufflebeam, D.L. & Anthony J. Shinkfield. (2007). *Evaluations Theory, strategies, and Applications*. 1st Edition. San Fransisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Teemant, A., Smith, M. E., Pinnegar, S., & Egan, M. W. (2005). Modeling Sociocultural Pedagogy in Distance Education. *Teachers College Record*, 107(8), 1675–1698. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9620.2005.00538.x>
- Veletsianos, G., Houlden, S., Hodson, J, Thompson, C.P., & Reid, D. (2022). An Evaluation of a Microlearning Intervention to Limit COVID-19 Online Misinformation. *Journal of Formative Design in Learning*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41686-022-00067-z>
- Voola, R., Casimir, G., Carlson, J., & Anushree Agnihotri, M. (2012). The Effects of Market Orientation, Technological Opportunism, and E-Business Adoption on Performance: A Moderated Mediation Analysis. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 20(2), 136–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ausmj.2011.10.001>